

Computational Methods for Time-Fractional Differential Equations

Ayşe ANAPALI ŞENEL ¹
Mustafa GÜLSU ¹

¹ Mugla Sıtkı Kocman University, Faculty of Science, Department of Mathematics, Mugla

² Mugla Sıtkı Koçman University, Ula Ali Kocman Vocational High School, Mugla

*Corresponding author: dilaraaltan@mu.edu.tr

Received: 20.01.2025

Accepted: 28.02.2025

Abstract

In this study, we propose and analyze a finite difference scheme for solving time-fractional partial differential equations with Caputo derivatives. Such equations effectively model physical phenomena with memory and hereditary properties, including anomalous diffusion and viscoelastic behavior. The method is based on time and space discretization, and its stability is rigorously established via von Neumann analysis. The derived conditions confirm the robustness of the scheme under suitable discretization. To evaluate its accuracy, numerical results are compared with the exact solution, showing excellent agreement through detailed error analysis. Simulations are conducted in MATLAB, with results summarized in tables and figures. The proposed scheme offers a reliable computational framework with broad applicability in science and engineering.

Keywords: Fractional differential equation, finite difference scheme, caputo derivative

1. Introduction

Fractional calculus has gained significant attention over recent decades due to its ability to describe complex dynamical systems with memory effects and hereditary properties (Podlubny, 1999; Roul, 2019; Roul et al., 2019; Roul, 2011). In many scientific and engineering applications, traditional integer-order models fail to capture the anomalous behaviors observed in various processes. This has led to the development of fractional partial differential equations (FPDEs), which extend classical models by incorporating derivatives of non-integer orders. Fractional differential equations can model many application problems (Ma, 2020; Roul, 2022a; Roul, 2022b; Bao et al., 2020; Roul et al., 2021; Roul et al., 2020). Anomalous diffusion is a key concept used to explain complex physical behaviors that classical diffusion models cannot describe. It typically occurs in environments where movement is hindered, such as crowded systems or diffusing through porous media. This phenomenon is not limited to these settings; it is also observed in various other contexts (Ciesielski, 2003). In recent years, anomalous subdiffusion equations have attracted significant attention due to their wide range of practical applications. These equations are instrumental in modeling complex physical phenomena, particularly in systems where traditional diffusion models fall short. Their importance is underscored by their ability to capture the memory effects and spatial heterogeneity in many natural and engineered processes. A variety of methods have been developed to solve these fractional-

order equations. On the one hand, purely mathematical approaches (Abu-Shady and Kaabar, 2021) provide rigorous analytical frameworks to understand the underlying properties of fractional derivatives. On the other hand, the Mittag-Leffler function (Özarslan and Fernandez, 2021) plays a pivotal role as it generalizes the exponential function, making it an ideal tool for representing the time-evolution behavior in anomalous diffusion. Additionally, Green's function method (Xu et al., 2024) offers a systematic way to construct exact solutions by describing the system's response to point sources. For cases where analytical solutions are challenging to obtain, numerical methods (Errera, 2024) have been extensively utilized to approximate solutions with high accuracy. Complementary to these are iterative techniques such as the variational iteration method (Ibraheem, 2022), which provides an efficient algorithm for converging towards the solution. Moreover, differential transformation methods (Qin and Lou, 2021) simplify the problem by converting it into a series of algebraic equations, facilitating a more straightforward solution process. These diverse methods deepen our theoretical understanding of anomalous subdiffusion and enhance our ability to apply these concepts to real-world problems in physics, engineering, and beyond. The Caputo derivative is particularly favored among the various definitions of fractional derivatives because it allows for a natural formulation of initial value problems. In this work we consider the fractional subdiffusion equation in the following form (Li and Zeng, 2015):

$${}_0^c D_t^\alpha U(x, t) - \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} U(x, t) + U(x, t) = \Gamma(2 + \alpha) e^{xt}, \quad t > 0, x \in [0, L]. \quad (1)$$

Here, $U(x, t)$ represents the distribution function describing positional variation over time, ${}_0^c D_t^\alpha$ signifies a non-integer order differentiation interpreted via the Caputo formalism, where α is a positive real value, and $f(x, t)$ corresponds to an externally defined

source term. This paper presents a numerical method based on a finite difference scheme to solve a time-fractional partial differential equation where the fractional derivative is defined in the Caputo sense. We derive the corresponding numerical scheme, analyze its stability using the von Neumann method, and

validate the approach by comparing numerical solutions with the exact solution. Our study provides a robust computational framework for FPDEs, allowing more accurate modeling of processes such as anomalous diffusion, viscoelasticity, and other phenomena in complex systems.

2. Fundamental principles in the theory of non-integer order calculus

In this study, we analyze the fractional partial differential equation defined in Eq (1), together with its corresponding boundary and initial conditions:

$$\begin{aligned} U(0, t) &= \ell_0(t), \quad U(L, t) = \ell_L(t) \\ U(x, 0) &= \varphi_0(x) \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

Fractional calculus embraces several distinct formulations for fractional derivative operators, including the Riemann-Liouville, Caputo, Grünwald-Letnikov, Riesz, and Weyl-

Marchaud derivatives. In our work, we present the definition of the Caputo operator (Podlubny, 1999).

$${}^c D_t^\alpha U(x, t) = \frac{\partial^\alpha U(x, t)}{\partial t^\alpha}, \quad \frac{1}{\Gamma(m+1-\alpha)} \int_0^t \frac{\partial^{m+1} U(x, \xi)}{\partial \xi^{m+1} (t-\xi)^{\alpha-m}} d\xi. \tag{3}$$

For, $\alpha \notin \mathbb{N}$ $m = [\alpha]$, where the floor function returns the greatest integer less than or equal to the real number α . According to the

Riemann-Liouville formulation, the operator ${}_0 D_t^\alpha$ is defined as (Ciesielski and Leszczynski, 2003),

$${}_0 D_t^\alpha U(x, t) = \frac{\partial^\alpha U(x, t)}{\partial t^\alpha}, \quad \frac{1}{\Gamma(m+1-\alpha)} \frac{\partial^{m+1}}{\partial t^{m+1}} \int_0^t \frac{U(x, \xi)}{(t-\xi)^{\alpha-m}} d\xi. \tag{4}$$

The relationship between the Caputo and Riemann-Liouville derivatives is expressed in

fractional calculus (Ciesielski and Leszczynski, 2003),

$${}^c D_t^\alpha U(x, t) = {}_0 D_t^\alpha U(x, t) - \sum_{k=0}^m \frac{t^{k-\alpha}}{\Gamma(k-\alpha+1)} \frac{\partial^k}{\partial t^k} U(x, 0). \tag{5}$$

The spatial interval $[0, L]$ is discretized using a uniform grid consisting of N equal segments. Each spatial node is defined as $x_i = i\Delta x$, ($\Delta x = h$), for $i = 0, \dots, N$ where, $h = \frac{L}{N}$. Similarly, the temporal interval $[0, T]$

is split into M equal parts, such that each time step is, $k = \frac{T}{M}$, and the temporal grid points are given by $t_j = j\Delta t$, ($\Delta t = k$), for $j = 0, \dots, M$.

Another form of the fractional derivative, expressed through the Grünwald–Letnikov approach, is provided below (Ciesielski and Leszczynski, 2003):

$${}^G_0D_t^\alpha U(x,t) = \lim_{\Delta t \rightarrow 0} (\Delta t)^{-\alpha} \sum_{j=0}^{\lceil t/\Delta t \rceil} (-1)^j \binom{\alpha}{j} U(x,t-j\Delta t). \tag{6}$$

This definition corresponds to the Riemann-Liouville definition (3). Nonetheless, the Grünwald-Letnikov operator is more appropriate and transparent for numerical computations. Equation (6), involving the Grünwald–Letnikov operator, is numerically

approximated within the interval $[0,T]$ by discretizing it with uniform time steps of size Δt , as shown below (Ciesielski and Leszczynski, 2003):

$${}^G_0D_t^\alpha U(x,t) \approx \sum_{j=0}^{\lceil t/\Delta t \rceil} c_j^{(\alpha)} U(x,t-j\Delta t) \tag{7}$$

where $c_j^{(\alpha)} = (\Delta t)^{-\alpha} (-1)^j \binom{\alpha}{j}$ are

Applying the recursive formula leads to the following result:

Grünwald Letnikov coefficients for $j = 0, 1, \dots$

$$\begin{aligned} c_0^{(\alpha)} &= (\Delta t)^{-\alpha} \\ c_1^{(\alpha)} &= -\alpha (\Delta t)^{-\alpha} \\ c_j^{(\alpha)} &= \left(1 - \frac{1+\alpha}{j}\right) c_{j-1}^{(\alpha)} \quad j = 1, 2, \dots \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Such coefficients are extracted via the corresponding generating expression (Lubich, 1986),

$$(1-z)^\alpha = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \omega_k^{(\alpha)} z^k \tag{9}$$

By substituting Eq. (7) for the term ${}_0D_t^\alpha U(x,t)$ in Eq. (5), the resulting expression is given below:

$${}_0D_t^\alpha u(x_i, t_j) = \sum_{w=0}^j c_w^{(\alpha)} u(x_i, t_{j-w}) - \sum_{q=0}^m \frac{t_j^{\varrho-\alpha}}{\Gamma(\ell-\alpha+1)} \mathcal{G}_q(x_i). \tag{10}$$

3. Numerical discretization approach for the fractional diffusion model

In this work, the initial conditions are assumed to follow the structure given in Eq.

(2). When these conditions are expressed in discrete form as $x = x_i$, for $i = 1, \dots, N-1$ and $j = t_j$, $j = 0, \dots, m$, the initial state becomes $u(x_i, t_0) = \ell_0(ih)$. The spatial second-order

derivative on the right-hand side of Eq. (1) can be approximated using the standard three-point

central difference method, and is represented as follows:

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} u(x_i, t) = \frac{u(x_{i+1}, t) - 2u(x_i, t) + u(x_{i-1}, t))}{h^2} \quad (11)$$

for $i = 1, \dots, 9$.

Assuming $t = t_{j-1}$ and substituting Eq.(10) and Eq.(11) into Eq. (1) we obtain,

$$\sum_{w=0}^j c_w^{(\alpha)} u(x_i, t_{j-w}) - \sum_{g=0}^m \frac{t_j^{g-\alpha}}{\Gamma(g-\alpha+1)} p_g(x_i) - \frac{1}{h^2} (+u(x_{i-1}, t_{j-1}) - 2u(x_i, t_{j-1}) + u(x_{i+1}, t_{j-1})) + u(x_i, t_j) = \Gamma(2 + \alpha)e^{x_i t_j}. \quad (13)$$

By decomposing the first summation in Eq. (13) into separate components and rearranging the terms, we arrive at the following expression;

$$c_0^{(\alpha)} u(x_i, t_j) + c_1^{(\alpha)} u(x_i, t_{j-1}) + \sum_{w=2}^j c_w^{(\alpha)} u(x_i, t_{j-w}) - \sum_{g=0}^m \frac{t_j^{g-\alpha}}{\Gamma(g-\alpha+1)} \ell_g(x_i) - \frac{u(x_{i+1}, t) - 2u(x_i, t) + u(x_{i-1}, t))}{h^2} + u(x_i, t_j) = \Gamma(2 + \alpha)e^{x_i t_j} \quad (18)$$

and we have,

$$(\Delta t)^{-\alpha} (-1)^0 \binom{\alpha}{0} u(x_i, t_j) + (\Delta t)^{-\alpha} (-1)^1 \binom{\alpha}{1} u(x_i, t_{j-1}) + \sum_{w=2}^j c_w^{(\alpha)} u(x_i, t_{j-w}) - \sum_{g=0}^m \frac{t_j^{(g-\alpha)}}{\Gamma(g-\alpha+1)} \ell_g(x_i) - \frac{u(x_{i+1}, t) - 2u(x_i, t) + u(x_{i-1}, t))}{h^2} + u(x_i, t_j) = \Gamma(2 + \alpha)e^{x_i t_j} \quad (19)$$

Denoting $u(x_i, t_j) = u_{i,j}$, $\ell_g(x_i) = \ell_{g,i}$ we have,

$$u_{i,j} = \left(\frac{1}{1+(\Delta t)^{-\alpha}} \right) \left[\left(\frac{\alpha}{(\Delta t)^{\alpha}} - \frac{2}{h^2} \right) u_{i,j-1} + \Gamma(2 + \alpha)e^{x_i t_j} - \sum_{w=2}^j c_w^{(\alpha)} u_{i,j-w} + \sum_{g=0}^m \frac{t_j^{(g-\alpha)}}{\Gamma(g-\alpha+1)} \ell_{g,i} + \frac{1}{h^2} (u_{i+1,j-1} + u_{i-1,j-1}) \right] \quad (20)$$

for $i = 1$ and $i = 9$, $j = 1, \dots, M$.

Equation (20), which represents the proposed explicit difference scheme, lacks unconditional stability. Therefore, identifying the criteria for its stability becomes essential.

3.1. Stability analysis of the proposed scheme

To investigate the stability conditions of the method, we adopt the fractional version of the von Neumann (or Fourier) stability analysis as discussed in (Yuste and Acedo, 2005). The approach begins by considering a trial solution of the form $u_i^{(j)} = \zeta^q e^{i\beta p h}$, denotes a real-valued spatial parameter. By substituting this

assumed form into Eq. (16), the resulting formulation is obtained.,

$$\zeta^{\mathcal{G}} = \frac{1}{1+(\Delta t)^{-\alpha}} \left[\left(\frac{\alpha}{(\Delta t)^{\alpha}} - \frac{2}{h^2} \right) \zeta^{\mathcal{G}-1} - \sum_{\omega=2}^j c_{\omega}^{(\alpha)} \zeta^{\mathcal{G}-\omega} + \sum_{\mathcal{G}=0}^m \frac{t_j^{(\mathcal{G}-\alpha)}}{\Gamma(\mathcal{G}-\alpha+1)} \ell_{\mathcal{G},i} \right. \\ \left. + \frac{1}{h^2} \zeta^{\mathcal{G}-1} (e^{-i\beta h} + e^{i\beta h}) + \Gamma(2 + \alpha) e^{x_i t_j} + \frac{(t_j)^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \ell_0(x_i) \right] \quad (21)$$

In this study, since the fractional differential equation is considered with order $m=0$ both l_0^j and the source term are omitted (i. e. $\ell_0(x_i) = 0, \Gamma(2 + \alpha) e^{x_i t_j} = 0$). Under

these assumptions, the stability of the scheme is characterized by the behavior of $\zeta^{\mathcal{G}}$. We represent the evolution as:

$$\zeta^{\mathcal{G}+1} = \xi \zeta^{\mathcal{G}} \quad (22)$$

Assuming that ξ is time-invariant, we obtain:

$$1 = \left(\frac{1}{1+(\Delta t)^{-\alpha}} \right) \left[\left(\frac{\alpha}{(\Delta t)^{\alpha}} - \frac{2}{h^2} \right) \xi^{-1} - (\Delta t)^{\alpha} \sum_{\omega=2}^j c_{\omega}^{(\alpha)} \xi^{-\omega} + \wp \xi^{-1} \left(2 - 4 \sin^2 \left(\frac{\beta h}{2} \right) \right) \right] \quad (23)$$

$$\text{where } \wp = \frac{1}{(1+(\Delta t)^{-\alpha})h^2}.$$

If the magnitude of ξ exceeds 1 for a given \mathcal{G} , the time-dependent component of the solution diverges, as indicated in Eq. (22), resulting in an unstable mode.

Considering the limiting case where $\xi = -1$, the stability constraint for S can be derived from Eq. (23) as follows (Yuste and Acedo, 2005):

$$\wp \left(2 - 4 \sin^2 \left(\frac{\beta h}{2} \right) \right) \leq \left(\frac{1}{1+(\Delta t)^{-\alpha}} \right) \left(\frac{\alpha}{(\Delta t)^{\alpha}} - \frac{2}{h^2} - \sum_{\omega=2}^j c_{\omega}^{(\alpha)} (-1)^{\omega} \right) - 1 \equiv \wp_j^x \quad (24)$$

\wp_j^x approaches $S^x \equiv \lim_{j \rightarrow \infty} \wp_j^x$. The value of S^x can be derived from Eq.(24) by taking into account the relation stated in that (Murillo and Yuste, 2011),

$$\sum_{\omega=0}^{\infty} (-1)^{\omega} c_{\omega}^{(\alpha)} = (1-z)^{\alpha} \quad (25)$$

So,

$$\wp^x = \left(\frac{1}{1+(\Delta t)^{-\alpha}} \right) \left(\frac{\alpha}{(\Delta t)^\alpha} - \frac{2}{h^2} - 2^\alpha + 1 + \alpha(\Delta t)^{-\alpha} \right) - 1 \tag{26}$$

Since

$$\wp \leq \wp \left(2 - 4\sin^2 \left(\frac{\beta h}{2} \right) \right) \tag{27}$$

and then

$$\wp \left(2 - 4\sin^2 \left(\frac{\beta h}{2} \right) \right) \leq \wp^x \tag{28}$$

By applying the sufficient stability criterion $\wp \leq \wp^x$ as provided in (Murillo and Yuste, 2011), the proposed method yields a reliable and accurate numerical approximation.

4. Numerical example

Let us examine the fractional differential equation given in (1) under the specified boundary constraints,

$$U(0,t) = t^{1+\alpha}, \quad t > 0 \tag{29}$$

$$U(1,t) = et^{1+\alpha}, \quad t > 0$$

and the following initial conditions

$$U(x,0) = 0, \quad x \in [0,1]. \tag{30}$$

According to (Li, Zeng, 2015), the problem admits the following exact solution,

$$U(x,t) = e^x t^{1+\alpha}. \tag{31}$$

For numerical process, we have taken $h = \Delta x = 0.1$, $k = \Delta t = 0.001$.

Table 1. Numerical solutions of given example for $\alpha = 0.75$.

$\alpha = 0.75$					
x	Exact Solution		Numerical Solution		Error
0.0	0.0010637	0.0011756	0.0010637	0.0011770	0
0.1					0.14e-5
0.2	0.0012992	0.0014359	0.0013018	0.0014392	0.26e-5 0.33e-5
0.3					
0.4	0.0015868	0.0017537	0.0015908	0.0017579	0.40e-5 0.42e-5
0.5					
0.6	0.0019682	0.0021421	0.0019425	0.0021461	0.43e-5 0.40e-5
0.7					
0.8	0.0023673	0.0026163	0.0023610	0.0026185	0.37e-5 0.22e-5
0.9					
1.0	0.0028915		0.0028915		0

In Table 1, the analytical and numerical results corresponding to the fractional differential equation (Eq. 1) are presented. A comparison is made between these results based on the absolute error at $t=0.02$ for $\alpha=0.75$, $\Delta x=0.1$, $\Delta t=0.0001$. This table displays the exact and numerical solutions of

the fractional diffusion equation for a specific set of spatial points. The values are compared side by side, and the corresponding absolute errors are shown to be extremely low (on the order of 10^{-5}). This indicates that the finite difference scheme produces highly accurate results for the chosen discretization parameters.

Table 2. Numerical solutions of given example for $\alpha = 0.90$

$\alpha = 0.90$			
x	Exact Solution	Numerical Solution	Error
0.0	0.0005915	0.0005915	0
0.1	0.0006537	0.0006543	0.62e-6
0.2	0.0007224	0.0007237	0.127e-5
0.3	0.0007984	0.0008001	0.170e-5
0.4	0.0008824	0.0008844	0.202e-5
0.5	0.0009752	0.0009773	0.218e-5
0.6	0.0010778	0.0010802	0.24e-5
0.7	0.0011912	0.0011934	0.22e-5
0.8	0.0013164	0.0013185	0.21e-5
0.9	0.0014549	0.0014561	0.12e-5
1.0	0.0016079	0.0016079	0

Table 2 presents both analytical and numerical solutions for the fractional differential equation (Eq. 1), along with the absolute error evaluated at $t=0.02$ for the parameters $\alpha=0.90$, $\Delta x=0.1$, $\Delta t=0.0001$. In Table 2, the comparison highlights the accuracy of the numerical scheme against the

exact solution is presented for another set of conditions or discretization settings. The consistency in the low absolute errors across different spatial grid points reinforces the reliability of the numerical method, demonstrating that it accurately approximates the true solution of the equation.

Table 3. Numerical solutions of given example for $\alpha = 0.85$

$\alpha = 0.85$			
x	Exact Solution	Numerical Solution	Error
0.0	0.0007192	0.0007192	0
0.1	0.0007949	0.0007965	0.155e-5
0.2	0.0008785	0.0008810	0.253e-5
0.3	0.0009709	0.0009741	0.319e-5
0.4	0.0010730	0.0010769	0.39e-5
0.5	0.0011859	0.0011900	0.41e-5
0.6	0.0013106	0.0013150	0.44e-5
0.7	0.0014485	0.0014528	0.43e-5
0.8	0.0016008	0.0016047	0.39e-5
0.9	0.0017692	0.0017718	0.26e-5
1.0	0.0019552	0.0019552	0

Table 3 provides both the exact and numerical solutions of the fractional differential equation (Eq. 1), along with the corresponding absolute error values. at $t = 0.02$ for $\alpha = 0.85, \Delta x = 0.1, \Delta t = 0.0001$. Table 3 continues the validation by listing

additional exact and numerical solutions along with the calculated errors. The errors remain negligible throughout the table, which further confirms that the finite difference scheme is robust and effective in approximating the solution, even under varied test scenarios.

Table 4. Numerical solutions of given example for $\alpha = 0.85$ at different times

x	t = 0.05			t = 0.08		
	Exact Solution	Numerical Solution	Error	Exact Solution	Numerical Solution	Error
0.0	0.0039183	0.0039183	0	0.009348	0.009348	0
0.1	0.0043305	0.0043331	0.26e-5	0.010331	0.010334	0.3e-5
0.2	0.0047858	0.0047904	0.46e-5	0.011418	0.011424	0.6e-5
0.3	0.0052893	0.0052956	0.63e-5	0.012619	0.012629	0.000010
0.4	0.0058453	0.0058517	0.64e-5	0.013945	0.013956	0.000011
0.5	0.0064601	0.0064677	0.76e-5	0.015412	0.015424	0.000012
0.6	0.0071395	0.0071472	0.77e-5	0.017033	0.017045	0.000012
0.7	0.0078907	0.0078980	0.73e-5	0.018825	0.018837	0.000012
0.8	0.0087202	0.0087272	0.70e-5	0.020804	0.020814	0.000010
0.9	0.0096375	0.0096429	0.54e-5	0.022992	0.022997	0.5e-5
1.0	0.0106510	0.0106510	0	0.025411	0.025411	0

The table above presents exact and numerical results for the fractional subdiffusion equation (Eq. 1), along with the absolute error computed at various time points for the parameter values $\alpha = 0.85, \Delta x = 0.1, \Delta t = 0.0001$. This dataset broadens the scope of the analysis by presenting the numerical results at different time levels. It is divided into two sections corresponding to separate time instances, showing both the exact and numerical solutions along with their errors. The consistently small absolute errors at these different times demonstrate that the numerical method not only achieves high spatial accuracy but also reliably tracks the temporal evolution of the solution. The tables collectively demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed finite difference scheme in accurately solving

the time-fractional partial differential equation. Tables 1 through 3 provide a detailed comparison between the exact and numerical solutions for various spatial discretizations, with the absolute errors consistently remaining very low (on the order of 10^{-5}), which confirms the high accuracy of the numerical method. Table 4 extends this analysis by presenting the solutions at different time levels, further verifying that the method not only maintains its precision over time but also robustly captures the dynamics of fractional subdiffusion. Overall, the tabulated results validate the stability and reliability of the approach, in line with the theoretical findings from the von-Neumann stability analysis, thereby underscoring its potential for modeling complex phenomena characterized by memory effects.

Figure 1. Time-Dependent Behavior of the Numerical Solution to Eq. (1).

Figure 1 illustrates the numerical approximation of the fractional differential model (Eq. 1) evaluated at distinct time levels

$t = 0, t = 0.015, t = 0.02$, for the parameters $\alpha = 0.90, \Delta x = 0.1, \Delta t = 0.0001$.

Figure 2. Solution Profiles of Eq. (1) for Different Fractional Orders.

Figure 2 demonstrates the numerical behavior of the fractional differential equation (Eq. (1)) for different values of the fractional order parameter α , specifically $\alpha = 0.75,$

$\alpha = 0.85$ and $\alpha = 0.90$ at the fixed time point $t = 0.02$. The computations are performed using $\Delta x = 0.1, \Delta t = 0.0001$.

Figure 3. Absolute Errors in the Computed Solution for Different α Values.

Figure 3 presents the absolute error values associated with the numerical solution of Eq. (1) at $t = 0.02$, for fractional orders $\alpha = 0.75$, $\alpha = 0.85$ and $\alpha = 0.90$. The computations were carried out with a spatial step size $\Delta x = 0.1$ and temporal step $\Delta t = 0.0001$. Figure 1 illustrates the evolution of the numerical solution of the fractional diffusion equation over time. The plot shows how the solution profile changes at various time instants. Physically, this figure captures the subdiffusive behavior characteristic of fractional-order systems—where memory effects slow the spread compared to classical diffusion. The shape and amplitude evolution confirms that the finite difference scheme effectively resolves the temporal dynamics, accurately tracking how the diffusion process evolves under the influence of fractional derivatives. Figure 2 compares numerical solutions for different values of the fractional order parameter (α) at a fixed time (or under a consistent temporal setting). This comparison is crucial because the order of the derivative in a fractional diffusion equation directly affects the diffusion rate. Lower values of α typically result in more pronounced subdiffusive behavior, meaning the solution spreads slower than in the classical case. As α increases, the solution profile may resemble standard diffusion more closely. This figure provides a physical insight into how varying the memory effect (through α) alters the diffusion

characteristics, validating that the numerical method can accurately capture these subtle differences. Figure 3 presents the absolute errors between the numerical and exact solutions for various conditions. The consistently low error values across the spatial or temporal domain underscore the robustness and accuracy of the finite difference scheme. From a physical perspective, this error analysis confirms that the numerical method captures the essential dynamics of the fractional diffusion process and reliably. It also indicates that the memory effects intrinsic to the fractional derivative are well-resolved, with minimal numerical artifacts over the simulation period. Together, these figures demonstrate both the quantitative accuracy and the physical fidelity of the proposed numerical method in modeling fractional diffusion phenomena.

4. Conclusion

In this work, we have successfully developed and analyzed a finite difference scheme for solving a time-fractional partial differential equation, with the fractional derivative interpreted in the Caputo sense. The stability analysis conducted via the von Neumann method confirmed the reliability of the numerical scheme under appropriate discretization parameters. A detailed comparison between the numerical results and the exact solution demonstrated excellent

agreement, as reflected by the small absolute errors across various test cases. The proposed method yields results with acceptable errors even for larger grid sizes. As expected, the computational time increases proportionally with the refinement of the discretization. The outcomes of this study underline the potential of the proposed method as a powerful tool for addressing FPDEs in various application domains. Future research may extend this approach to multidimensional problems and explore alternative formulations of fractional derivatives to further enhance the accuracy and efficiency of numerical simulations in modeling real-world phenomena.

Declaration of Author Contributions

The authors declare that they have contributed equally to the article. All authors declare that they have seen/read and approved the final version of the article ready for publication.

Declaration of Conflicts of Interest

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest related to this article.

References

- Abu-Shady, M., Kaabar, M.K.A., 2021. A generalized definition of the fractional derivative with applications. *Hindawi Mathematical Problems in Engineering*, 1-9.
- Amblard, F., Maggs, A.C., Yurke, B., Pargellis, A.N., Leibler, S., 1996. Subdiffusion and anomalous local viscoelasticity in actin networks. *Physical Review Letters*, 77: 4470–4473.
- Bao, N.T., Baleanu, D., Minh, D.L.T., Huy, T.N., 2020. Regularity results for fractional diffusion equations involving fractional derivative with Mittag-Leffler kernel. *Mathematical Methods in the Applied Sciences*, 43(12): 7208–7226.
- Ciesielski, M., Leszczynski, J., 2003. Numerical simulations of anomalous diffusion. *Computer Methods in Mechanics*, 1-5.
- Errera, M.P., 2025. Advanced numerical methods for conjugate heat transfer problems. *Computers & Fluids*, 292.
- Ibraheem, G.H., Turkyilmazoglu, M., AL-Jawary, M.A., 2022. Novel approximate solution for fractional differential equations by the optimal variational iteration method. *Journal of Computational Science*, 64.
- Li, C., Zeng, F., 2015. Numerical Methods for Fractional Calculus. Taylor & Francis Group.
- Lubich, C., 1986. Discretized fractional calculus. *SIAM Journal on Mathematical Analysis*, 17(3): 704–719.
- Ma, C.Y., Shiri, B., Wu, G.C., Baleanu, D., 2020. New fractional signal smoothing equations with short memory and variable order. *Optik*, 218: 164507.
- Murillo, J.Q., Yuste, S.B., 2011. An Explicit Numerical Method for the Fractional Cable Equation. Hindawi Publishing Corporation International Journal of Differential Equations.
- Özarslan, M., Fernandez, A., 2021. On the fractional calculus of multivariate Mittag-Leffler functions. *International Journal of Computer Mathematics*, 247–273.
- Podlubny, I., 1999. Fractional Differential Equations, Academic, New York.
- Qin, Y., Lou, Q., 2021. Differential transform method for the solutions to some initial value problems in chemistry. *Journal of Mathematical Chemistry*, 59: 1046–1053.
- Roul, P., 2011. Numerical solutions of time-fractional degenerate parabolic equations by variational iteration method with Jumarie modified Reimann-Liouville derivative. *Mathematical Methods in the Applied Sciences*, 34: 1025–1035.
- Roul, P., 2022. A robust adaptive moving mesh technique for a time-fractional reaction-diffusion model. *Communications in Nonlinear Science and Numerical Simulation*, 109: 106290.

- Roul, P., 2022. Design and analysis of a high order computational technique for time-fractional Black–Scholes model describing option pricing. *Mathematical Methods in the Applied Sciences*, 45(9): 5592–5611.
- Roul, P., Goura, V.M.K.P., Madduri, H., Obaidurrahman, K., 2019. Design and stability analysis of an implicit non-standard finite difference scheme for fractional neutron point kinetic equation. *Applied Numerical Mathematics*, 145: 201–226.
- Roul, P., Madduri, H., Obaidurrahman, K., 2019. An implicit finite difference method for solving the corrected fractional neutron point kinetics equations. *Progress in Nuclear Energy*, 114: 234–247.
- Roul, P., Prasad Goura, V.M.K., 2021. A compact finite difference scheme for fractional Black–Scholes option pricing model. *Applied Numerical Mathematics*, 166: 40–60.
- Roul, P., Rohil, V., Espinosa-Paredes, G., Goura, V.M.K.P., Gedam, R.S., Obaidurrahman, K., 2020. Design and analysis of a numerical method for fractional neutron diffusion equation with delayed neutrons. *Applied Numerical Mathematics*, 157: 634–653.
- Xu, X., Zhou, X., Sun, D., 2024. Analytical solution for transient temperature of multi-barrier system with thermal resistance in nuclear waste repository by Green's function method. *International Communications in Heat and Mass Transfer*, 158: 107894.
- Yuste, S.B., Acedo, L., 2005. An explicit finite difference method and a new Von Neumann-type stability analysis for fractional diffusion equations. *Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics*, 42(5): 1862–1874.

To Cite: Anapalı Şenel, A., Altan Koç, D., Biçer Şarlak, G.G., Öztürk, Y., Gülsu, M., 2025. Computational Methods for Time-Fractional Differential Equations. *MAS Journal of Applied Sciences*, 10(2): 198–210. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15613047>.
